

ON THE HIGHER-DIMENSIONAL GENERALIZATION OF A PROBLEM OF ROTH

József Borbély

*Department of Algebra and Number Theory, Eötvös Lóránd University,
Budapest, Hungary*

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Abstract

Long ago Roth conjectured that for any k -coloring of the positive integers the equation $x + x' = n, x \neq x'$ has a monochromatic solution in (x, x') for more than cM integers n up to M (where c is an absolute constant independent of k). Later Erdős, Sárközy and T. Sós proved this conjecture with $\frac{1}{2} - \varepsilon$ in place of c . In this paper we will prove a higher-dimensional generalization of this theorem by using a higher-dimensional extension of the well known Hilbert cube-lemma. We will also give bounds for the number of monochromatic solutions in higher dimension.

1. Introduction

K. F. Roth conjectured (see [2] and [6]) that for an arbitrary k -coloring of the positive integers there are more than cM integers $n \leq M$ such that the equation $x + x' = n, x \neq x'$, has a monochromatic solution in (x, x') . In [1] Erdős, Sárközy and T. Sós proved this conjecture in the following form:

Theorem 1. *For every $k \geq 2$ there exists a positive integer $M_0(k)$ such that for any $M \geq M_0(k)$ and an arbitrary k -coloring of the set \mathbb{N} , the number of positive integers $n \leq M$ for which there is a monochromatic solution of the equation $x + x' = n, x \neq x'$, is greater than $\frac{M}{2} - 3M^{1-2^{-k-1}}$*

The proof of this theorem was based on the density version of Hilbert's cube lemma (for the original coloring version see [7]). Szemerédi proved that if we consider a sequence of positive integers of positive density, then the sequence must contain a so-called Hilbert d -cube or affine d -cube, i.e., for every d a set of the form $u + \sum_{i=1}^d \varepsilon_i v_i$, where $\varepsilon_i = 0$ or 1 for every i . In [7] Hilbert used the coloring version of this lemma in studying irreducibility of polynomials with integer coefficients. Later, Szemerédi gave the density version of this lemma (see [3] and [10]). This density version of Hilbert's cube lemma is generally called Szemerédi's cube lemma. Erdős, Sárközy and T. Sós used the following quantitative version of this lemma:

Lemma 1. (Szemerédi’s cube lemma): *If H is a subset of $(1, M)$ for M large enough and H has at least $3M^{1-2^{-d}}$ elements, then H contains a Hilbert-cube.*

Our first goal is to give a higher-dimensional generalization of Lemma 1. With this generalization we will prove the following result:

Theorem 2. *For fixed positive integers r, s, k , there is a positive integer m_0 with the following property: for any positive integer $m > m_0$ and for any k -coloring of the elements of the set $(1, m)^r$ there are at least $\lfloor \frac{m}{s} \rfloor^r - 3 \cdot (2^{r-1}m^r)^{1-2^{-ks+k-1}}$ vectors \vec{x} in $(1, m)^r$, such that one can find pairwise distinct vectors $\vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_2, \dots, \vec{x}_s$ of the same color in $(1, m)^r$, whose sum is \vec{x} .*

The special case $r = 1$ and $s = 2$ in Theorem 2 gives the result of Theorem 1. After the proof of Theorem 2 we will study the number of solutions of the equation $\vec{x} + \vec{x}' = \vec{n}, \vec{x} \neq \vec{x}'$ for vectors \vec{n} in $(1, m)^r$, where \vec{x} and \vec{x}' are monochromatic. We will get the following result:

Theorem 3. *For every positive real number α and β with the property $\alpha^r + \beta^r \leq \frac{1}{2^{2r+1}k}$ there is a positive integer $m_{\alpha\beta}$, such that for every $m > m_{\alpha\beta}$ and for every k -coloring of \mathbb{N}^r the number of elements in $(1, m)^r$ having representations as a sum of two monochromatic distinct vectors in more than $\frac{\beta^r}{2}m^r$ ways is more than $\alpha^r m^r$.*

One can observe that the result of Theorem 2 is asymptotically independent of the number of the colors, if we fix r and s . In Theorem 3 we want to search for an arbitrary k -coloring a “large number” of vectors with a “large number of representations”. Here we will see that these “large numbers” already depend on the number of the colors for fixed r and s . First we study only the case of two summands, later we show a way of studying the case of more summands.

2. The Generalization of Hilbert’s Cube Lemma

Similarly to the original definition one can interpret d -cubes in the set of r -dimensional vectors.

Definition 1. If $\vec{u}, \vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2, \dots, \vec{v}_d$ are r -dimensional vectors, then the set of the sums in the form $\vec{u} + \sum_{i=1}^d \varepsilon_i \vec{v}_i$, where $\varepsilon_i = 0$ or 1 for every i , is an affine d -cube or a d -dimensional Hilbert cube.

Lemma 2. *If H is a subset of distinct vectors of $(1, m)^r$ and the set H has at least $3 \cdot (2^{r-1}m^r)^{1-2^{-d}}$ elements, then H contains an affine d -cube.*

Proof. Our proof is a generalization of the proof given in [1]. We will define sets H_0, H_1, \dots, H_d and r -dimensional vectors $\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2, \dots, \vec{v}_d$ in the following way:

- (i) $H_0 = H$
- (ii) $H_j \cup \{\vec{b} + \vec{v}_j | \vec{b} \in H_j\}$ is a subset of H_{j-1} for every $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$
- (iii) $|H_j| \geq |H|^{2^j} (3 \cdot 2^{r-1} m^r)^{-(2^j-1)}$

We construct H_0, H_1, \dots, H_d and $\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2, \dots, \vec{v}_d$ recursively. Let $H_0 = H$. Assume that $0 \leq j \leq d - 1$ and in the case $j > 0$ sets H_0, H_1, \dots, H_j and vectors $\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2, \dots, \vec{v}_j$ have been defined. Let F be the set of the vectors in $(-(m - 1), (m - 1))^r$, whose first nonzero coordinate is positive. Denote by $f(H_j, \vec{h})$ the number of solutions of the equation $\vec{b} - \vec{b}' = \vec{h}$, where $\vec{b}, \vec{b}' \in H_j$ and $\vec{h} \in F$.

Let L be the maximum value of the numbers $f(H_j, \vec{h})$, where $\vec{h} \in F$ and $\vec{h} \neq \vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2, \dots, \vec{v}_j$. For all r -dimensional vectors \vec{h} we have $f(H_j, \vec{h}) \leq |H_j|$. Clearly $\sum_{\vec{h} \in F} f(H_j, \vec{h}) = \binom{|H_j|}{2}$. We give an estimate for L . We can majorize $f(H_j, \vec{h})$ by $|H_j|$, if $\vec{h} \in \{\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2, \dots, \vec{v}_j\}$ and by L otherwise. Thus we get the estimate

$$\binom{|H_j|}{2} \leq j |H_j| + \frac{(2m - 1)^r - 1}{2} L < j |H_j| + 2^{r-1} m^r L.$$

Thus we have $L \geq \frac{1}{2^r m^r} (|H_j|^2 - |H_j| - 2j |H_j|) = \frac{|H_j|}{3 \cdot 2^{r-1} m^r} (\frac{3}{2} |H_j| - \frac{3}{2} - 3j)$. According to our assumption we have (for m large enough) the estimate

$$\begin{aligned} |H_j| &\geq |H|^{2^j} (3 \cdot 2^{r-1} m^r)^{-(2^j-1)} > \left(3 \cdot (2^{r-1} m^r)^{1-2^{-d}}\right)^{2^j} (3 \cdot 2^{r-1} m^r)^{-(2^j-1)} \\ &= 3 \cdot (2^{r-1} m^r)^{1-2^{j-d}} > 3 \cdot (2^{r-1} m^r)^{1-2^{-1}} > 3 + 6d > 3 + 6j. \end{aligned}$$

So we have $\frac{|H_j|^2}{3 \cdot 2^{r-1} m^r} < L$. By (iii) we get $L > |H|^{2^{j+1}} (3 \cdot 2^{r-1} m^r)^{-(2^{j+1}-1)}$. This means that the vector \vec{h} can play the role of \vec{v}_{j+1} and we are able to define set H_{j+1} , too. Thus indeed we can define sets H_0, H_1, \dots, H_d and r -dimensional vectors $\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2, \dots, \vec{v}_d$ recursively. \square

3. The Proof of the Generalization of Roth's Problem

Here we give a proof of Theorem 2.

Proof. Assume to the contrary that there is an appropriate k -coloring for infinitely many positive integers m , such that the number of vectors \vec{x} with the given property in $(1, m)^r$ is less than $\left[\frac{m}{s}\right]^r - 3 \cdot (2^{r-1} m^r)^{1-2^{-ks+k-1}}$. We will get a contradiction via Lemma 2. Let S be the subset of $(1, m)^r$, in which all the r coordinates of the elements are divisible by s . Let S' denote the set of those elements of S , which do

not have a representation in the given form. According to our assumption we have $3 \cdot (2^{r-1}m^r)^{1-2^{-ks+k-1}} < |S'|$. Now we can apply Lemma 2. In S' one can find an affine $(ks-k+1)$ -cube, so that there are r -dimensional vectors $\vec{u}, \vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2, \dots, v_{ks-k+1}$ in $(-(m-1), (m-1))^r$, such that all the sums $\vec{u} + \sum_{i=1}^{ks-k+1} \varepsilon_i \vec{v}_i$ are in S' , where $\varepsilon_i=0$ or 1 for every i . By the pigeonhole principle there are s vectors in the set $\{\frac{1}{s}\vec{u} + \vec{v}_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, ks-k+1\}$ with the same color. We can assume without loss of generality, that these vectors are $\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2, \dots, \vec{v}_s$. By the definition of the Hilbert-cube the vector $\vec{u} + \sum_{i=1}^s \vec{v}_i = \sum_{i=1}^s (\frac{1}{s}\vec{u} + \vec{v}_i)$ is an element of S' , which contradicts the definition of S' . \square

4. On the Number of Representations as the Sum of Two Monochromatic Distinct Vectors

In this section we study the number of representations, if the number of summands is $s = 2$. Our goal is to prove Theorem 3. The key will be the following lemma:

Lemma 3. *If for positive real numbers α and β there exist infinitely many positive integers m , such that there is a k -coloring of \mathbb{N}^r , for which at most $\alpha^r m^r$ elements of $(1, m)^r$ have representations as a sum of two monochromatic distinct vectors of \mathbb{N}^r in more than $\frac{\beta^r}{2} m^r$ ways, then $\alpha^r + \beta^r > \frac{1}{2^{2r+1}k}$.*

Proof. Let be m a positive integer with the given property. Let a be the minimal and b the maximal positive integer such that $\frac{a}{m} \geq \alpha$ and $\frac{b}{m} \leq \beta$. In this case at most a^r elements of $(1, m)^r$ have representations as a sum of two monochromatic distinct vectors in more than $\frac{b^r}{2}$ ways. Let $f(\vec{x})$ denote the number of representations of $\vec{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_r)$ as the sum of two distinct vectors in $(1, x_1) \times (1, x_2) \times \dots \times (1, x_r)$. Clearly $f(\vec{x}) = \left\lfloor \frac{\prod_{i=1}^r (x_i - 1)}{2} \right\rfloor$, because one can order the vectors of this set (except at most one vector) into disjoint pairs such that each pair consists of two distinct vectors with sum \vec{x} . For all vectors \vec{x} of the set $(1, m)^r$ let $g(\vec{x})$ denote the number of representations of \vec{x} as the sum of two distinct monochromatic vectors of $(1, m)^r$. Let m_i be the number of vectors with the i -th color in $(1, \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor)^r$. Clearly $\sum_{i=1}^k m_i = \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor^r$ and $\sum_{i=1}^k \binom{m_i}{2} \leq \sum_{\vec{x} \in (1, m)^r} g(\vec{x})$. We give an upper estimate for the sum $\sum_{\vec{x} \in (1, m)^r} g(\vec{x})$, too. If one can write the vectors $\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2, \dots, \vec{v}_t (t \leq a^r)$, in more than $\frac{b^r}{2}$ ways as the sum of two monochromatic distinct vectors, then

$$\sum_{i=1}^t g(\vec{v}_i) \leq \sum_{\vec{x} \in (m-a+1, m)^r} f(\vec{x}).$$

Hence we have the following upper estimate:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{\vec{x} \in (1,m)^r} g(\vec{x}) &\leq \frac{b^r}{2} (m)^r + \sum_{\vec{x} \in (m-a+1,m)^r} f(\vec{x}) \\
 &\leq \frac{b^r}{2} m^r + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{x_r=m-a+1}^m \cdots \sum_{x_1=m-a+1}^m (x_1-1)(x_2-1)\cdots(x_r-1) \\
 &= \frac{b^r}{2} m^r + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{x_r=m-a}^{m-1} \cdots \sum_{x_1=m-a}^{m-1} x_1 x_2 \cdots x_r = \frac{b^r}{2} m^r + \frac{1}{2} \left(am - \frac{a^2+a}{2} \right)^r \\
 &< \frac{b^r}{2} m^r + (am)^r.
 \end{aligned}$$

Using the Cauchy-Schwarz-inequality we get

$$\sum_{i=1}^k \binom{m_i}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^k m_i^2 - \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{m}{2} \right]^r \geq \frac{1}{2} k \left(\frac{\left[\frac{m}{2} \right]^r}{k} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{m}{2} \right]^r.$$

By dividing by m^{2r} we get

$$\frac{\frac{1}{2} k \left(\frac{\left[\frac{m}{2} \right]^r}{k} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{m}{2} \right]^r}{m^{2r}} < \frac{\frac{1}{2} b^r m^r + \frac{1}{2} (am)^r}{m^{2r}}.$$

If m tends to infinity, then the left-hand side is asymptotically $\frac{1}{2^{2r+1}k}$ and the right-hand side is asymptotically $\frac{1}{2}\beta^r + \frac{1}{2}\alpha^r$. Clearly we have $\frac{1}{2}\beta^r + \frac{1}{2}\alpha^r < \alpha^r + \beta^r$, and hence $\alpha^r + \beta^r > \frac{1}{2^{2r+1}k}$. \square

With Lemma 3 we can easily prove Theorem 3. The proof can be done in the following way:

Proof. Assume, for a contradiction, that there are positive numbers α and β such that $\alpha^r + \beta^r \leq \frac{1}{2^{2r+1}k}$ and for infinitely many positive integers m there is a k -coloring of \mathbb{N}^r such that the number of elements in $(1, m)^r$ having representations as a sum of two monochromatic distinct vectors in more than $\frac{\beta^r}{2} m^r$ ways is at most $\alpha^r m^r$. This contradicts Lemma 3. \square

Remark. Let k' be the maximal odd integer such that $k \geq k'$. We color the elements of \mathbb{N}^r with at most k colors in the following way: if the sum of the coordinates is 0 or 1 modulo k' , then we color this vector by the first color; the other vectors are colored by the other $k' - 1$ colors according to the other residue classes. In this case there are at most $3 \cdot \left\lfloor \frac{m}{k'} \right\rfloor m^{r-1}$ vectors in $(1, m)^r$, for which the number of representations as a sum of two distinct monochromatic vectors is at least $2 \cdot \left\lfloor \frac{m}{k'} \right\rfloor m^{r-1}$ (to see this, one should only observe the vectors having the sum of coordinates equal to 0, 1 or 2 modulo k'). Thus Theorem 2 cannot be improved significantly.

5. Further Remarks

We studied in the last section only the case $s = 2$ (i.e., the number of addends is two). We can do calculations in a similar way using the further asymptotic formulae (see [9]). The method we use will not be combinatorially new, one needs only the same technique, but with a little more work. Let us denote by $p(n, s)$ the number of partitons of n into exactly s not necessarily distinct parts and $q(n, s)$ the number of partitons of n into exactly s distinct parts. We formulate the relevant statements of [9] in Lemma 4.

Lemma 4. $p(n, s) \sim \frac{n^{s-1}}{(1 \cdot 2 \cdots (s-1))^2 \cdot s}$ and $q(n, s) \sim \frac{n^{s-1}}{(1 \cdot 2 \cdots (s-1))^2 \cdot s}$ where $n \gg 1$ and $s = O(1)$.

We give only a sketch of how our methods generally work. Let $H(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_r)$ denote the number of representations of the vector $\vec{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_r)$ as a sum of s distinct vectors in $(1, x_1) \times (1, x_2) \times \dots \times (1, x_r)$. Let m_i be the number of vectors with the i -th color in $(1, \lfloor \frac{x_i}{s} \rfloor)^r$. It is obvious that $\sum_{i=1}^k \binom{m_i}{s} \leq \sum_{\vec{x} \in (1, m)^r} T(\vec{x})$, where $T(\vec{x})$ is the number of ways vector \vec{x} can be written as a sum of s monochromatic distinct vectors. A similar argument to that of Section 4 shows that we have to majorize $H(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_r)$.

It is easy to verify that

$$q(x_1, s) \prod_{i=2}^r (1 \cdot 2 \cdots s \cdot q(x_i, s)) \leq H(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_r) \leq p(x_1, s) \prod_{i=2}^r (1 \cdot 2 \cdots s \cdot p(x_i, s)).$$

By Lemma 4 we get the conclusion that $H(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_r)$ is asymptotically equal to

$$\frac{x_1^{s-1}}{(1 \cdot 2 \cdots (s-1))^2 \cdot s} \prod_{i=2}^r \left(1 \cdot 2 \cdots s \frac{x_i^{s-1}}{(1 \cdot 2 \cdots (s-1))^2 \cdot s} \right),$$

if s is fixed and $x_i \gg 1$. With further calculation one can achieve analogous results as formulated in Theorem 3.

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